

CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE ASSESSMENT OF GRASSLANDS PRODUCTIVITY FROM CĂPĂȚÂNII MOUNTAINS

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Abstract

The permanent grasslands in the central-southern part of the Căpățâni Mountains located between 450-2 120 m altitude are rich in plant species, registering a number of 54 cormophytes in the 163 associations described. The general coverage with vegetation was 95%, of which 60% were valuable forager species and 35% harmful to the grass carpet. At the level of phytosociological alliances (habitats), the highest forage green mass (GM) productions were evaluated for *Agrostion stoloniferae* (17.2 t/ha), *Arrhenatherion elatioris* (12.9 t/ha) and *Cynosurion cristati* (12.2 t/ha) that allow an average load of 1.1-1.5 LU/ha. The lowest GM yields of 0.3-0.4 t/ha with a loading below 0.1 LU/ha were in *Filipendulo-Petasition* and *Calthion palustris*. The achievable milk production was 68-80 hectoliters per hectare for the three best alliances with the highest GM and PV production shown above. Very low results in milk production were evaluated in alliances with the lowest VM productions and the lowest PV indices presented earlier. The data regarding the evaluation of economic productivity indices (GM, PV, LU/ha, Milk/ha) continue to serve for the correct preparation of pastoral arrangements and the optimal management of mountain grasslands.

Keywords: mountain grasslands, production of green mass and milk assessment, pastoral value

INTRODUCTION

Until now, numerous studies have been carried out on the inventory and classification of mountain meadow vegetation by geobotanists that include little or no data on grass production and its forage quality (Doniță et al. 1992; Coldea et al. 2012).

The floristic surveys carried out on the ground can still be used to evaluate the productivity of these meadows, according to a new method (Marușca 2019, 2022).

The production data of green mass and forage value are imperatively necessary for the preparation of pastoral arrangements and further for the proper grassland management (Marușca et al. 2014).

In the last 5 years, several assessments of the mountain grassland productivity in the Southern Carpathians have been carried out (Marușca et al. 2020a, 2022a; Marușca, Vințan 2022).

The present scientific paper is an addition to the knowledge about the pastoral value, green mass and milk production of grassland in the Căpățâni Mountains.

The research on grasslands vegetation had as its main objective the floristic composition with the establishment and classification of phylogenesis according to the Braun Blanquet – Tuxen phytosociological method, especially with concrete economic data that further serve to draw up pastoral arrangements and the appropriate management of this important way of using mountain agricultural land.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The evaluation of grasslands productivity is based on the doctoral thesis entitled “Flora and vegetation of the superior basin of the Luncavaț River (Căpățanii Mountains)”, prepared by biologist Mariana Niculescu, under the guidance of Prof. university Vasile Cristea, Faculty of Biology-Geography of the “Babeș-Bolyai” University in Cluj-Napoca, supported in 2016.

The method of studying the grassland vegetation was the geobotanical one following the Braun Blanquet – Túxen phytosociological school (Cristea et al. 2004).

The overview of practical vegetation is as follows:

JUNCETEA TRIFIDI Klika et Hadač 1944

CARICETALIA CURVULAE Br.-Bl. 1925

Caricion curvulae Br.-Bl. 1925

1. *Primulo-Caricetum curvulae* Br.-Bl. 1926 em Oberd. 1957
2. *Potentillo chrysocraspedae-Festucetum airoidis* Boșcaiu 1971
3. *Oreochloo-Juncetum trifidi* Szafer et al. 1956

NARDO-CALLUNETEA Preising 1949

NARDETALIA Oberd. 1949

Potentillo ternatae-Nardion strictae Simon 1957

4. *Pöetum mediae* Csűrös et al. 1956
5. *Scorzonero roseae-Festucetum nigricantis* (Pușcaru et al. 1956) Coldea 1987
6. *Violo declinatae-Nardetum strictae* Simon 1966

MOLINIO-ARRHENATHERETEA Tx. 1937

MOLINIETALIA W. Koch 1926

Calthion palustris Tx. 1936 em. Oberd. 195732.

7. *Carici flavae-Eriophoretum latifolii* Soó 1944
8. *Scirpetum silvatici* Schwick. 1944

Holco-Juncion Pass. 1964

9. *Caricetum brizoidis* O. Rațiu 1966
10. *Holcetum lanati* Issler 1936

Agrostion stoloniferae Soó (1943) 1971

11. *Agrostetum stoloniferae* (Ujvárosi 1941) Burduja et al. 1956
12. *Festucetum pratensis* Soó (1938) 1955, 1969

ARRHENATHERETALIA Pawl. 1928

Arrhenatherion elatioris (Br.-Bl. 1925) W. Koch 1926

13. *Poëtum pratensis* Răvăruț et al. 1956 (Syn. *Trifolio-Poëtum pratensis* (Răvăruț et al. 1956, Resmeriță 1958)

Filipendulo-Petasion Br.-Bl. 1947

14. *Chaerophylletum hirsuti* (Soó 1927) (Syn. *Chaerophyllo hirsutum- Equisetetum palustre* Vicol et Stoicovici 1977)

Cynosurion cristati Br.-Bl. Et Tx. 1943

15. *Anthoxantho-Agrostetum capillaris* Sillinger 1933, Jurko 1969

16. *Festuco rubrae-Agrostetum capillaris* Csürös-Káptalan 1964 (Syn. *Festucetum rubrae-Agrostietum capillaris* Horv. 1951; *Festuco rubrae-Cynosuretum* auct. roman., *Festucetum rubrae* et *Agrostis capillaris* auct. roman).

The 16 associations, 8 alliances, 4 orders and 3 more important vegetation classes were found. The synthetic floristic surveys were the basis for the grassland productivity evaluation according to the new method also described in the present Journal of Montology (Marușca et al. 2020 b).

The estimates regarding the abundance-dominance of the species in the grassy carpet measured according to the Braun-Blanquet scale were transformed into percentages, so that they could be processed statistically. (Cristea et al. 2004).

Next to each species in the tables, ratings were given for the forrage value from 4 to 9 and for harmful from 1 to 3, based on which, the pastoral value was calculated (Kovacs 1979; Păcurar, Rotar 2014; Marușca 2016) .

In the same way, appreciation notes were given for the phytomass of each species from 1 to 9, based on which mass indices were calculated and then the green mass production t/ha, of a phytosociological association (Marușca 2019,2022, Marușca et al.,2021). For grassland used for grazing with animals, the optimal duration of the grazing season (Dgs) was established, which is equal to the duration of the period with an average air temperature greater or equal to 10 up to 20 degrees Celsius (Marușca 2001).

After carrying out experiments for over 20 years, with milk cows at the “Teodor Marușca” mountain grassland research base, Blana-Bucegi, at 1800 m altitude, with an average grazing season of 85 days, a conversion index was established in the amount of 51.24 statistically ensured for the production of cow's milk made exclusively with grass from the subalpine pasture without any other additional forage to the ration (Marușca et al. 2018).The ratio 5,24 as a conversion index, between pastoral value (PV) and cow milk production in 85 days of grazing (Dgs) is 0.6 representing the calculation formula:

$$\text{Milk production (L/ha)} = \text{PV} \times \text{Dgs} \times 0.6$$

On altitudinal levels at the 100-2100 m difference in the Carpathians, the following grazing season durations with green mass requirements and fodder-milk conversion indices resulted (Table 1).

Table 1. Grazing season duration, green mass requirement and conversion coefficients depending on the grassland altitude (original)

Altitude (m)	Grazing season (days)	Necessary (GM)(kg/LU)	The PV and GM Conversion Coefficient in milk
100	115	7475	69.3
200	130	8450	78.4
300	145	9425	87.4
400	160	10400	96.4
500	175	11375	105.5
600	167	10855	100.7
700	160	10400	96.4
800	152	9880	91.6
900	145	9425	87.4
1000	137	8905	82.6
1100	130	8450	78.4
1200	122	7930	73.5
1300	115	7475	69.3
1400	107	6955	64.5
1500	100	6500	60.3
1600	92	5980	55.5
1700	85	5525	51.2
1800	77	5005	46.4
1900	70	4550	42.2
2000	62	4030	37.4
2100	55	3575	33.2

The optimal animal loading was determined by the formula:

$$\text{Animal Loading (LU/ha)} = (\text{GM production kg/ha} / (\text{Dsp} \times 65)),$$

where 65 is the daily requirement of green mass (GM) for the large livestock unit (LU), taking into account annual and seasonal fluctuations of the climate with periods of drought and disturbances in the constant provision of forage in the isolated mountain areas.

Finally, the productivity results evaluated at the association level were synchronized at the level of phytocyanological alliances that are closer to EU grassland habitats (Gafta, Montfort 2008).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In a first stage, the natural conditions of the practical associations (altitude, exposure, inclination of the slopes) with the number of cormophyte species and vegetation cover are briefly presented (Table 2).

Table 2. General natural conditions of grassland associations in the Căpățanii Mountains

No.	Grassland associations	Survey No.	Altitude (m)	Exposition	Inclination	Cormophyte	Coverage
<i>Al. Caricion curvulae</i>							
1	<i>Primulo minima-Caricetum curvulae</i>	10	2110 (2090-2120)	PL,V,NV,SV	4 (0-10)	42	96
2	<i>Potentillo chrysocraspedae-Festucetum airoidis</i>	20	1960 (1800-2100)	PL,S,SV,E, V,SE	7 (0-15)	48	93
3	<i>Oreochloo distichae-Juncetum trifidi</i>	15	2070 (1950-2120)	PL,V,SV,N,SE	8 (0-25)	37	92
<i>Al. Potentillo ternatae-Nardion strictae</i>							
4	<i>Poetum mediae</i>	15	1910 (1800-2000)	S,PL,SV,SE,E	9 (0-20)	46	97
5	<i>Scorzonero rosae-Festucetum nigricantis</i>	15	1740 (1500-1920)	S,SV,PL,SE,V,E	10 (0-25)	60	98
6	<i>Violo declinatae-Nardetum strictae</i>	20	1790 (1500-1950)	SV,S,E,SE, PL,NE	10 (0-20)	62	99
<i>Al. Calthion palustris</i>							
7	<i>Carici flavae-Eriophoretum latifolii</i>	5	1740 (1700-1750)	S,PL,V	3 (0-7)	29	85
8	<i>Scirpetum sylvatici</i>	10	620 (550-700)	PL,SV	1 (0-5)	52	98
<i>Al. Holco-Juncion</i>							
9	<i>Caricetum brizoides</i>	5	520 (500-550)	PLAN	0	23	100
10	<i>Holcetum lanati</i>	8	680 (550-750)	PL,SV,V	3 (0-7)	35	94
<i>Al. Agrostion stoloniferae</i>							
11	<i>Agrostidetum stoloniferae</i>	5	620 (480-750)	PLAN	0	67	98
12	<i>Festucetum pratensis</i>	10	500 (460-550)	PL,S,SV,SE	3 (0-7)	83	98
<i>Al. Arrhenatherion elatioris</i>							
13	<i>Poetum pratensis</i>	6	640 (450-1100)	PL,S,E	3 (0-10)	72	92
<i>Al. Filipendulo-Petasition</i>							
14	<i>Chaerophylletum hirsuti</i>	5	1360 (1100-1870)	PL,SV,S	9 (0-20)	43	84
<i>Al. Cynosurion cristati</i>							
15	<i>Anthoxantho-Agrostetum capillaris</i>	5	590 (450-900)	PL,S,SV	2 (0-5)	66	99
16	<i>Festucetum rubrae-Agrostietum capillaris</i>	9	680 (480-1100)	PL,SV,E,S,V	7 (0-15)	94	100
Average-Total		163	1220 (450-2120)	ALL	5 (0-25)	54	95

The altitudinal difference is between 450 to 2 120 m, with an average of 1 200 m, on all exposures and average inclination from the plane to 25 degrees with a very varied geomorphology. The average number of cormophyte species per association is 54, being considered quite high in terms of phytodiversity. The highest number of cormophytes was recorded in the associations *Festucetum rubrae - Agrostetum capillaris* (94 sp.), *Festucestum pratensis* (87 sp.), *Poetum pratensis* (72 sp.) and the lowest in *Caricetum brizoides* (23 sp.), *Carici flavae – Eriopharetum latifolii* (29 sp.) and *si Holcetum lanati* (35 sp.). Average vegetation cover was 95%, rated as very good with variations from 84% to 100%.

The average participation of forage species was 60% and of harmful 35%, with large variations between associations (Table 3).

Table 3. Participation of forage species, green mass production and the pastoral value of grassland associations

No.	Grassland associations	Species structure (%)		Grassland associations		Green mass production (t/ha)	Grazing season (days)	Optimal loading (LU/ha)
		Forager	Harmful	Ind.	%			
<i>Al. Caricion curvulae</i>								
1	<i>Primulo minima-Caricetum curvulae</i>	88	8	48.48	115	1.94	55	0.54
2	<i>Potentillo chrysocraspedae-Festucetum airidis</i>	78	15	43.66	103	2.75	65	0.65
3	<i>Oreochloa distichae-Juncetum trifidi</i>	81	11	37.69	89	2.08	60	0.53
<i>Al. Potentillo ternatae-Nardion strictae</i>								
4	<i>Poetum mediae</i>	77	20	44.24	105	3.69	70	0.81
5	<i>Scorzonero rosae-Festucetum nigricantis</i>	70	28	53.40	126	10.49	85	1.90
6	<i>Viola declinatae-Nardetum strictae</i>	15	84	10.25	24	1.27	80	0.24
<i>Al. Calthion palustris</i>								
7	<i>Carici flavae-Eriophoretum latifolii</i>	1	84	1.84	4	0.02	85	0.01
8	<i>Scirpetum sylvatici</i>	8	90	4.68	11	0.77	170	0.07
<i>Al. Holco-juncion</i>								
9	<i>Caricetum brizoides</i>	12	88	8.73	21	1.28	175	0.11
10	<i>Holcetum lanati</i>	93	1	64.22	152	14.99	160	1.44
<i>Al. Agrostion stoloniferae</i>								
11	<i>Agrostidetum stoloniferae</i>	82	16	63.96	151	13.23	170	1.20
12	<i>Festucetum pratensis</i>	94	4	87.20	206	21.08	175	1.85
<i>Al. Arrhenatherion elatioris</i>								
13	<i>Poetum pratensis</i>	82	10	70.15	166	12.92	165	1.20
<i>Al. Filipendulo-Petasion</i>								
14	<i>Chaerophylletum hirsuti</i>	3	81	1.99	5	0.31	110	0.04
<i>Al. Cynosurion cristati</i>								
15	<i>Anthoxantho-Agrostetum capillaris</i>	95	4	68.62	162	11.27	170	1.02
16	<i>Festucetum rubrae-Agrostietum capillaris</i>	88	12	66.94	158	13.14	160	1.26
AVERAGE		60	35	42.25	100	6.95	135	0.82

The best participation of forage species of 93-95% in the grass carpet was found in the associations *Anthoxantho-Agrostetum capillaris*, *Festucetum pratensis* and *Holcetum lanati* and those with 84-88% participation of harmful non-forage species were in the associations *Caricetum brizoide*, *Carici flavae - Eriophoretum latifolii* and *Violo declinataea - Nardetum strictae*, properties that directly influence pastoral value and the production of green mass. The pastoral value average was 42.25 (medium) and the green mass average production was 6.95 t/ha (poor). The highest pastoral value of 87.2 (very good) was evaluated in the *Agrostetum stoloniferae* association, and between 68.6 and 70.2 (good) in *Arrhenatheretum cristati*. At the opposite pole with 2-5 PV index (degraded) was *Carici flavae-Eriophoretie latifolii*, *Chaerophyletum hirsuti* and *Scirpetum sylvatici*.

The highest production of green mass (GM) of 21 t/ha was evaluated in the *Festucetum pratensis* association followed by productions of 12-13 t/ha in *Agrostetum stoloniferae* and *Poetum pratensis*. Very low productions of 0.1 -1.3 t/ha GM were recorded in associations with the lowest PV and the highest production of harmful plants in the grass carpet that we do not list here. The duration average of the grazing season (Dgs) at the level of the associations was estimated at 135 days, respectively 55 days in the subalpine zone up to 175 days in the premontane nemoral zone. The average load with animals was 0.82 LU/ha, quite high, with very large differences from 0.1 - 1.85 LU/ha depending on the GM and Dgs productions of the associations

A clearer analysis on MV production and animal loading LU/ha is at the level of phytosociological alliances that resemble habitats in the European sense (Table 4).

Table 4. Green mass production and optimal animal loading in the grazing season at the phytosociological alliance level

Phytosociological alliance	Altitude (m)	Species structure (%)		Green mass production (t/ha)	Optimal loading (LU/ha)
		Forager	Harmful		
<i>Caricion curvulae</i>	2045	82	11	2.26	0.57
<i>Potentillo -Nardion</i>	1815	54	44	5.15	0.98
<i>Calthion palustris</i>	1180	5	87	0.40	0.04
<i>Holco-Juncion</i>	600	53	45	8.14	0.78
<i>Agrostion stoloniferae</i>	560	88	10	17.16	1.53
<i>Arrhenatherion elatioris</i>	640	82	10	12.92	1.20
<i>Filipendulo-Petasition</i>	1360	3	81	0.31	0.04
<i>Cynosurion cristati</i>	635	92	8	12.21	1.14
AVERAGE	1105	57	37	7.32	0.79

By calculations was resulted an average production of 7.32 t/ha GM and a animal loading of 0.79 LU/ha at the alliance (habitat) level.

The most valuable proved to be *Agrostion stoloniferae* with 17.2 t/ha GM and 1.5 LU/ha, followed by *Arrhenatherion elatioris* with 1.2 LU/ha and *Cynosurion cristati* with 1.1 LU/ha. With productions of 0.3-0.4 t/ha GM were *Filipendulo-Petasition* and *Calthion palustris*.

A final and most important indicator of grassland productivity was the production of animals during the grazing season, in our case cow's milk (table 5).

Table 5. Pastoral value and cow's milk production of phytosociological alliances level, possible to achieve

Phytosociological alliance	Duration of grazing season (days)	Milk conversion coefficient (indices)	Pastoral value (indices)	Milk production (L/ha)
<i>Caricion curvulae</i>	60	38	43.28	1645
<i>Potentillo-Nardion</i>	78	49	35.96	1760
<i>Calthion palustris</i>	128	79	3.26	255
<i>Holco-Juncion</i>	168	103	36.48	3740
<i>Agrostion stoloniferae</i>	173	106	75.58	7975
<i>Arrhenatherion elatioris</i>	165	101	70.15	7085
<i>Filipendulo-Petasition</i>	110	67	1.99	135
<i>Cynosurion cristati</i>	165	101	67.78	6845
AVERAGE	131	81	41.81	3390

In the studied area, 68-80 hectoliters (HL) of milk per hectare were evaluated in the most valuable alliances (*Cyrsion*, *Arrhenatherion* and *Agrostion stoloniferae*) and barely 1.3-2.6 HL/ha in the degraded ones (*Filipendulo -Petasition*, *Calthion*) directly proportional to the production of GM and PV index described before.

The data in this paper serve mainly to compare and describe the level of productivity indices between grassland associations and alliances.

All these evaluations of grassland productivity at the phytocyanological association and alliance level can further serve for the inventory and economic mapping of grassland area in order to establish the average (general) productivity and the optimal loading with animals during the grazing season.

CONCLUSION

- The grasslands situated in the superior basin of the Luncavaț river located between 450-2120 m altitude have on average 54 species of cormophytes in the 163 associations described;

- The highest phytodiversity was recorded in the association *Festucetum rubrae - Agrostetum capillaries* (94 sp) and *Festucetum pratensis* (83 sp) and the lowest in *Caricetum brizoides* (23 sp) and *Carici flavae - Eriophoretum latifolii* (29 sp);

- The average production at the alliance level (habitat) was evaluated at 7.3 t/ha of green mass that can support 0.8 LU/ha and 130 days of grazing season;

- The average pastoral value of the alliances was almost 42, which ensures the achievement of 34 hectoliters of milk per hectare.

- The highest production was evaluated in the *Agrostion stoloniferae* alliance which is 17.16 t/ha green mass with a pastoral value of 75.58 which allows the achievement of 8,010 liters/ha in 173 days of grazing season and the lowest in *Filipendula-Petasition* of barely 135 liters/ha in 110 days of grazing season, with a load of 0.04 UVM/ha;

- These economic data of plant and animal productivity of mountain meadows, continue to serve for the preparation of pastoral arrangements and their efficient management.

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